

Determinants of Customer Satisfaction in Microfinance Banks of Pakistan

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Abstract:

The leading indicator of loyalty and repurchase intention is customer satisfaction. This study is focused on identification of basic factors or areas which determine the customer satisfaction in microfinance banking industry. Data was collected through a standard questionnaire from 149 customers of 30 branches of 3 major microfinance banks. SPSS 16 was used for data analysis. Results concluded that microfinance banks policies and procedures, the physical appearance of the bank branch, empathy and commitment of staff with the customers are major factors which determine the customer satisfaction in microfinance banks.

Keywords: Customer satisfaction, Microfinance, Banking industry, Pakistan.

Introduction:

Smart companies know that customer satisfaction is the leading path to profitability and prosperity; historically it is known that companies which have highly satisfied “customer base” are earning above the average profit while ignoring its importance may be very costly to firms. Especially in banking sectors where there is fierce competition, more demanding customers, and the changing climate have presented an unparalleled set of challenges (lovelock, 2001) for banks. Therefore the only ticket to profitability, the path to prosperity & way to survive in such a highly competitive world; resides with satisfaction.

(Parker; Mathew, 2001) expressed that there are two basic definitional approaches of the concept of customer satisfaction. The first approach defines satisfaction as a process and the second approach defines satisfaction as an outcome of a consumption experience. These two approaches are complementary, as often one depends on the other. (Parker; Mathews, 2001) however noted that the process of satisfaction definitions concentrates on the antecedents to satisfaction rather than satisfaction itself. Satisfaction as a process is the most extensively adopted explanation of customer satisfaction, and a lot of research efforts have been directed at understanding the process approach to satisfaction evaluations (Parker; Mathews, 2001). This approach has its origin in the discrepancy theory (Porter, 1961), which argued that satisfaction is determined by the opinion of a difference between some standard and actual performance. (Cardozo, 1965); and (Howard; Sheath, 1969) developed the contrast theory, which showed that consumers would exaggerate any contrasts between expectations and product evaluations.

(Olshavsky & Miller, 1972); And Olson and Dover (1979) developed the assimilation theory, which means that perceived quality is straight rising with hope. Assimilation effects occur when the difference between hope and worth is too small to be supposed.

(Anderson, 1973) Additional developed this theory into assimilation-contrast theory, which means if the inconsistency is too large to assimilate then the distinction effects occur. The assimilation-contrast effect occurs when the difference between prospect and quality is too large to be declared, and this difference is overstated by consumers.

Similarly, Microfinance sector across the world and specifically in Pakistan has also recognized the importance of customer satisfaction. The focus of microfinance banks has been shifted from customer acquisition to establishing, maintaining and long lasting, satisfying relationship with its customers. Considering the importance of customer satisfaction a very little research work has been carried out in the context of microfinance banks in Pakistan. Therefore the focus of this study is to address this issue and identify factors that contribute to customer satisfaction in microfinance banking industry.

Literature Review:

Henning et al., (1997) Said customer satisfaction has moderate relation with customer relationship, whereas relationship quality is a three-dimensional variable, which includes product-service related quality perception, customer trust, and relationship commitment. (Caruana, 2002) Said customer satisfaction has four constructs; expectations, performance, disconfirmation, and satisfaction. He further describes that customer satisfaction performs a mediating role in the link between service quality and service loyalty, whereas service quality is one of the important antecedents for customer satisfaction. (Ruth, 1998) Wrote that customer satisfaction decision to cancel or stay loyal to the provider is positively related to the duration of the relationship. Customers who have many months experience with organization weigh prior satisfaction more heavily and few less heavily. Therefore organizations should focus on customers in the early stages of the relationship. If the customer experience is not satisfactory the relationship is likely to be short. (Robert, 1996) Explained eighteen determinants of service quality. In the banking industry the effectiveness, responsiveness, care, and friendliness are the source of satisfaction. The intangible aspects of the staff-customer interface have significant positive and negative effects on service quality and customer satisfaction. There is need to engender a helpful, caring, friendly and committed approach in staff. (lee, lee, & yoo, 2000) Concluded that perceived service quality, in fact, leads to satisfaction. The service quality is an antecedent for customer satisfaction, and customer satisfaction has a strong influence on purchase intention. Customer satisfaction is also influenced by factors like price, convenience, and availability. They recommended that companies should spend more on improving customer satisfaction to increase repurchase intentions because customer retention is cost-effective than to attract a new customer. They also added that in service industry responsiveness is the most important customer satisfaction factor. (Robert h. , 1996) Wrote that customer satisfaction creates customer loyalty, which increases the company's profitability. In order to measure the customer satisfaction, researchers need to work closely with the organization to develop exemplary measurement system. (Fornell, Jhonson, Michael, Anderson, & eugene, 1996) Customer satisfaction is greater for goods than for services and in turn, greater for services than for government agencies. They found that while determining the customer satisfaction customization is more important than reliability. Customer satisfaction is more quality-driven than value or price-driven. And customer expectation plays a greater role in sectors in which variance in production and consumption is low. (Kurt & Elmar, 2002) Concluded that customer satisfaction consists of three factors. Basic factors are minimum requirements that cause dissatisfaction if not fulfilled but do not lead to customer satisfaction if fulfilled. Basic factors are considered prerequisite by the customers in any product. Performance factors lead to satisfaction if fulfilled and lead to dissatisfaction if not fulfilled. Excitement factors increase customer satisfaction if delivered but do not cause dissatisfaction if they are missing. (Thorsten & Tharau, 2004) According to his developed model customer orientation of service, the employee is an important determinant of customer satisfaction in the service industry. Service employees of an organization should be trained on the development of their technical, social and motivational skills and given necessary authority to make decisions. (Kazi, 2011) Concluded that empathy, responsiveness, reliability, assurance and tangibility of a bank's staff are positively related to customer satisfaction. The increase in these service quality attributes increases the level of customer satisfaction. (Kazi, 2011) Concluded that service quality, corporate image and customer value of a bank are positively related to customer satisfaction and loyalty. Whenever there is an increase in these elements, the customer satisfaction also increases. Josee Bloemer, Ko de Ruyter and Pascal Peeters (1998) concluded that reliability and position in the market are relatively important drivers of the bank loyalty. Bank image is related to loyalty via perceived quality whereas service quality is related to loyalty via satisfaction. Service quality has a direct effect on bank loyalty. Fahmi Shaaban Fararah (2014) concluded that in Yemen the business development services provided by the Islamic Microfinance Banks are the main source of satisfaction among customers. They need these services in order to survive, grow and repay the money back to these banks. Fahmi Shaaban Fararah & Abdullah Kaid Al-Swidi (2013) argued that there is a significant effect of service quality on customer satisfaction and perceived benefits mediates the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in Islamic Microfinance Banks in Yemen. Muhammad Toufiqul Islam, Chikako Takanashi & Takashi Nakori (2013) elaborated costs and price, responsiveness, conditions, human relations, reliability, and tangibles has the important factors that affect customer satisfaction in microfinance industry in Bangladesh. Muhammad Sharif Bashir, Muslichah

Muhammad Machali and Abdul Rehman Mohammad Mwinyi (2012) concluded that in microfinance industry of Kenya the service quality has the significant positive effect on customer satisfaction. People consider service quality has a most important factor when going to any microfinance bank. (Hsin & Yi, 2006) Argued that in m-commerce industry in Taiwan perceived value and trust are the two factors which affect customer satisfaction and in turn customer satisfaction has a positive effect on customer loyalty. (Sogunro & Abioda, 2014) Shortlisted seven factors in the insurance industry which determine the level of customer satisfaction; low price, flexible payment structure, benefit of death and survival, customer service, profit sharing, special scheme benefit and tax reduction benefit. (Zhaohua, Yaobin, Kwok, & Jinlong, 2010) Concluded that in mobile instant messaging services the trust, perceived service quality and the perceived, functional, emotional, social and monetary value are the factors which determine customer satisfaction. (Abraham & Taylor, 1999) Measured the customer satisfaction in the hospitality industry, where they rated service quality dimensions; reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangibles as important factors which affect customer satisfaction.

Research Objectives

- To explore the underline dimension and determinants of customer's satisfaction in Microfinance institution of Pakistan.
- To test the proposed model, Impact of MFB policy and procedure, Employees Empathy, Physical Appearance, Employees Commitment on Customer's Satisfaction.
- To find out which determinants contribute more towards customer's satisfaction in Microfinance Institution.

Fig.1. Proposed Conceptual Model for Determinants of customer's Satisfaction in Microfinance Institution

Research Hypothesis

H1: MFB policy and procedure tend to positively influence customer's satisfactions in Microfinance Institution.

H2: Employees Empathy tend to positively influence customer's satisfactions in Microfinance Institution

H3: Physical Appearance tend to positively influence customer's satisfactions in Microfinance Institution

H4: Employees Commitment tend to positively influence customer's satisfactions in Microfinance Institution

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Sample Selection/targeted respondents

Our target respondents were the customers of different microfinance banks operating in the country. The sample includes customers from rural and urban markets, different age groups, both male and female, having diversified businesses, educated and illiterate and customers are having experience of dealing with the microfinance banks from less than a year and up to 10 years.

3.2. Sampling technique

Non-probabilistic convenient sampling technique was used.

3.3. Sample size

Keeping in mind the size of the market and number of microfinance banks operating in the country 149 customers were selected as sample. That sample includes customers of 3 major microfinance banks operating the country.

3.4. Research Instrument

A standard research questionnaire was used to collect the data from work done by Mr. Owusu-Boateng, Kwame in July 2012 on topic "An assessment of customer satisfaction in microfinance industry."

3.5. Data collection

Data was collected from customers of 30 branches of 3 major microfinance banks.

3.6. Data Analysis

SPSS 16 was used for data analysis.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1. Demographics Profile of Respondents

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the respondents who participated in this survey. It can be seen from the table, 78.5% (n = 117) of the respondents were males whereas the 21.5% (n = 32) of the respondents were females. 12.8% (n = 19) of the respondents were between the age of 18 to 25, 42.3% (n = 63) of the respondents were between the age of 26 to 35, whereas 24.8% (n = 37) of the respondents were between 36 to 45 years of age, 14.8% (n = 22) of the respondents were between 46 to 55 years of age And 5.4% (n = 08) of the respondents were above 56 years of age, who participated in this survey. Moreover, 9.4% (n = 14) of the respondents are customers of microfinance institution since less than a year. 36.2% (n = 54) of the respondents are customers of microfinance institution since 1 to 2 years, 16.8% (n = 25) of the respondents are customers of microfinance institution since 3 to 4 years, and 37.6% (n = 56) of the respondents are customers of microfinance institution since above 4 years. Furthermore, 28.9% (n = 43) of the respondents were Illiterate, 24.2% (n = 36) of the respondents had education till primary school, 22.8% (n = 34) of the respondents' education level was Metric 14.1% (n = 21) of the respondents' education was Intermediate and 10.1% (n = 15) of the respondents' education level was bachelor and above. In addition to that 24.8% (n = 37) of respondents' occupation was farming and 75.2% (n = 12) of the respondents' occupation was non-farming who participated in this survey.

Table-1 Demographic Characteristic of Respondents

Demographics	N	%
Gender		
Male	117	78.5
Female	32	21.5
Age		
18 to 25	19	12.8
26 to 35	63	42.3
36 to 45	37	24.8
46 to 55	22	14.8
56 and Above	8	5.4
Customer's Since		
Less than a Year	14	9.4
1 to 2 Years	54	36.2
3 to 4 Years	25	16.8
Over 4 Years	56	37.6
Education		
Illiterate	43	28.9
Primary	36	24.2
Metric	34	22.8
Intermediate	21	14.1
Bachelor and Above	15	10.1
Occupation		
Farming	37	24.8
Non-Farming	112	75.2

Table 2 shows the reliability of the variables/ constructs under study; these variables were tested by using Corn Bach's alpha, as shown in Table 2 relatively high reliability coefficient values have been observed. The Corn Bach's Alpha of the MFB Policy and Procedures is .870 (6). Similarly, the Corn Bach's alpha for Employees Empathy is .923 (4). Physical Appearance's Corn Bach's alpha is .964 (3); Employees Commitment has an alpha of .842 (4), and finally, Customer's Satisfaction Corn Bach's alpha is .713. The overall Corn Bach's alpha coefficients of the all variables are the more than the standard 0.7 (Churchill, 1979; Nunnally, 1978) which show high level of reliability of the variables/construct

Table.2. Reliability Coefficient for the Variables under Study

Construct/Variable	Number of Items	Reliability Coefficient
MFB Policy and Procedures	6	.870
Employees Empathy	4	.923
Physical Appearance	3	.964
Employees Commitment	4	.842
Customer's Satisfaction	2	.713

4.2. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

The study performed Factor Analysis using a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) alongside with Varimax, Kaiser Normalization rotation method until the Eigenvalue of each factor was equal to 1 or more, particularly table 3 shows the result of the Factor Analysis of determinants of customer's satisfaction in microfinance Institution of Pakistan, which represents the five-factor solution. The first factor MFB policies and procedure, has the highest variance explain of 25.460 with an eigenvalue of 4.837 which include loan

requirements, turnaround time, interest rates, pre-disbursement conditions, insurance policy and application & processing fee. Initially the first factor contained 7 items, the factor loading of item “loan repayment schedule of MFB” had the lowest factor loading which indicates that the customers are not satisfied with the repayment schedule of Microfinance banks in Pakistan, therefore this item had been removed from further analysis as it does not meet the minimal level ($< .30$) for interpretation of structure (Hair et al, 1998). Similarly, the factor 2 Employees Empathy explains 18.118% of the variance with 3.442 eigenvalues which consisted of four items, MFB staff members are “helpful”, “Courteous”, “Friendly” and “Polite”. The factor 3 Physical Appearance explains 16.386% variance with 3.113 eigenvalues. The factor 3 contains three items including “MFB branch are at a convenient location”, “MFB Banking hall is transaction friendly” and “Satisfaction towards banking hall temperature, seating arrangements and so on”. Factor 4, Employees Commitment explains 11.097% of variance with 2.108 eigenvalue, which contains four items including “The knowledge level of MFB staff members are very high”, “MFB staff members explain the product features and benefits clearly”, “MFB deliver what they promise”, and “I am satisfied with the available products of MFB”. Finally, the factor 5, Customer’s Satisfaction explains 6.901% of the variance with 1.311 eigenvalues. Customer’s Satisfaction factor contains two items which represent the satisfaction towards microfinance banks in Pakistan. Moreover, the KMO and Bartlett’s Test for determinants of customer’s satisfaction in microfinance institution is .738 ($\chi^2=249.633$), respectively with a significant level of $p < 0.000$. Hence, KMO and Bartlett’s test are considered as a good in explaining the sample used in this factor analysis is adequate.

Table.3. Exploratory Factor Analysis for Determinants of Customer’s Satisfaction

Items	MFB Policy	Employees Empathy	Physical Appearance	Employees Commitment	Customer’s Satisfaction
I am satisfied with the loan application and processing fee of MFB	.937				
I am satisfied with the loan requirement of MFB.	.891				
I am satisfied with MFB transaction turnaround time.	.859				
I am satisfied with the interest rates of MFB.	.840				
I am satisfied with the pre-disbursement conditions of MFB.	.812				
I am satisfied with the loan insurance policy of MFB in the case of death/disability.	.718				
MFB bank staff members are very helpful		.960			
MFB bank staff members are very courteous		.957			
MFB staff members are highly friendly		.859			
MFB staff members are very polite		.829			
MFB branch are at a convenient location			.972		
MFB Banking hall is transaction friendly			.950		

Banking hall temperature, seating arrangements, drinking water availability and toilet facility.						.933
MFB deliver what they promise.						.842
The knowledge level of MFB staff members are very high						.832
MFB staff members explain the product features and benefits clearly						.807
I am satisfied with the available products of MFB						.745
I am satisfied with the overall MFB services						.770
In general, I am satisfied with MFB.						.651
Eigenvalues	4.837	3.442	3.113	2.108	1.311	
% of Variance Explain	25.460	18.118	16.386	11.097	6.901	
Cumulative % of Variance	25.460	43.579	59.964	71.061	77.962	

Note: K-M-O Measure of sampling adequacy = .738; Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity = 249.633: $p < 0.000$

4.3. Multiple Regression Analysis

Considering the outcome of the factor analysis, the items for independent variables and the dependent variable (customer’s satisfaction) were aggregated in which factor loadings exceeded .30 were retained for further analysis. The multiple regression analysis was conducted to reveal which variables are the determinants of customer’s satisfaction in Microfinance institution In Pakistan.

Table.4. Multiple Regression Analysis Statistics

Variables	Standardized β	t-value	P-value	Partial	Part
(Constant)		5.456	.000		
MFB Policy and Procedures	.491	7.962	.000	.553	.481
Employees Empathy	.187	2.879	.005	.233	.174
Physical Appearance	.129	2.121	.036	.174	.128
Employees Commitment	.414	6.429	.000	.472	.388
F-value	32.491(.000)				
R Square	.474				
Adjusted R square	.460				

a. Predictors: (Constant), Employees Commitment, Employees Empathy, Physical Appearance, MFB Policy

b. Dependent Variable: Customers Satisfaction

Table.4. shows the results of Standardized Multiple Regression; particularly In H1, it is proposed that MFB policy and procedure have a positively significant impact on customer’s satisfaction. The measured coefficient of MFB policy and procedure is 0.491 with t -value of 7.962, which is significant at the $p < 0.000$ level, suggesting that MFB policy and procedures have a strong, unique contribution to explaining customer’s satisfaction in microfinance institutions of Pakistan. Thus the H2 is supported. Similarly, in H2, It is proposed that Employees Empathy has a positively significant impact on customer’s satisfaction. The measured

coefficient of Employees Empathy is .187 with t -value of 2.897, which is significant at the $p < 0.005$ level, suggesting that Employees Empathy is also unique contribute to explain customer's satisfaction in microfinance institutions of Pakistan, thus the H2 is supported. In H3, It is proposed that MFB banking's Physical Appearance has a significant effect on customer's satisfaction, t -value is 2.121, which is significant at the $p < .036$ level, the standardized coefficients is .129 indicating that physical appearance has a unique contribution to explaining customer's. Thus H3 is supported. Finally, in H4, It is proposed that Employees Commitment has a positively significant impact on customer's satisfaction. The standardized coefficients of Employees Commitment is .414 with t -value of 6.429, which is significant at the $p < 0.000$ level, suggesting that Employees Commitment has strong, unique contribution in explaining customer's satisfaction in microfinance institutions of Pakistan. Thus the H4 is supported (see figure.2)

Moreover the R-square is .474 suggests that MBF policy and procedures, Employees Empathy, physical appearance and employees commitment are explaining 47.4% of the variance in predicting the customer's satisfaction, in other words, the customer's satisfaction in microfinance institutions can be predicted by four independent variables which include MBF policy and procedures, Employees Empathy, physical appearance and employees commitment. In addition to that, the F-test value is 32.491 at a p-value of 0.000, suggesting the model is statistically significant.

Fig.2. Estimated Model for Determinants of Customer's Satisfaction in Microfinance Institution

5. Conclusion:

Customer satisfaction is the heart of any business, and in services sector like banking, it is something very challenging to measure. Microfinance banking sector has seen a tremendous growth in the country in last 15 years and so. In this study, we have made an attempt to identify the determinants of the customer satisfaction in microfinance banking in Pakistan. We have concluded that customer satisfaction with microfinance banks consists of four major factors or areas; 1) Microfinance Banks policies and procedures which include product pricing, turnaround time, documents requirement and pre-disbursement formalities, 2) Empathy level of the staff with customers that include the extent to which the bank staff is helpful, friendly, polite and courteous to its customers, 3) Physical appearance and environment of the branch of the bank also matters and finally 4) Level of staff commitment to the customers, which consists of staff knowledge about the banks products and communication to customers about benefits and features of these products. It is witnessed that whenever customer approaches a microfinance bank and purchase any product, these four factors are most likely which will determine the level of customer satisfaction with the bank.

Limitations and Future Research:

The research was conducted at only the microfinance banks with four independent variables which are MFB policies and procedures, Employee commitment, employee empathy and physical appearance. For future research, it is suggested to the researchers that they may take some other variables to know the responses from customers and from different industries.

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